

Exploring Open Access eBook Usage Toward a Common Framework

Chambers Meeting Room
Sheraton Tribeca, New York, NY
December 3-4, 2018

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Exploring Open Access eBook Usage Toward a Common Framework

Objectives

- Strengthen relationships between Open Access ebook stakeholders
- Develop understandings among stakeholders regarding their different perspectives and goals regarding the measurement of engagement with Open Access ebooks
- Identify key impediments to aggregating, analyzing, and communicating information about OA ebook engagement
- Identify and prioritize activities stakeholders might engage in to lower those barriers
- Stress-test a possible “data trust” idea for ongoing cross-stakeholder collaboration, including consideration of its potential form, function, and governance and business models.

Outcomes

- An informal network of Open Access ebook stakeholders who are willing to align some of their efforts to collaboratively pursue joint goals
- A draft “Joint Strategy” Brief that begins to document shared goals, priority activities, and the stakeholders involved in each (focusing on attendees but leaving room for future expansion to additional players)
- Scoping documentation for at least one pilot project(s) to pursue (partners, deliverables, timelines)

Pework

- Please read: [Building a Trusted Framework for Coordinating OA Monograph Usage Data](#) (KU Research).
- Please put an “out of office” message on your email and plan to be mostly deviceless for the working portions of this convening.

Presentations:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1MYPwuqMj32WEJTITHmImiURIYXSUQ7oQ?ogsrc=32>

Participants

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Agenda

Day 1, December 3

08:00 - 08:30	Breakfast and coffee
08:30 - 09:30	Welcome, Agenda, Introductions
09:30 - 10:15	Working Session 1: Understanding the Need
10:15 - 10:40	Walk-and-Talk
10:40 - 11:00	Break
11:00 - 12:00	Working Session 2: Inputs and Outputs
12:00 - 12:30	Walk-and-Talk
12:30 - 01:30	Lunch
01:30 - 02:30	Mini-Presentations: Understanding What Exists Today <ul style="list-style-type: none">● COUNTER 5 (Lorraine Estelle)● OPERAS/HIRMEOS (Pierre Mounier)● IRUS (Ross MacIntyre)● Knowledge Unlatched OA Usage Tool (Sven Fund)● Crossref Event Data (Jennifer Lin)
02:30 - 03:00	Break
03:00 - 04:00	Working Session 3: Joint Goals, Joint Strategies
04:00 - 04:40	Presentation and Discussion: Collaborative Models KU Research
04:40 - 05:00	Alignment Check
5:00 - 6:30	Break
6:30	Summit Dinner (Pera Soho, 54 Thomson Street, New York, NY 10022)

Agenda

Day 2, December 4

08:00 - 08:30	Breakfast and coffee
08:30 - 09:00	Brief reflections on day 1
09:00 - 09:45	<i>Working Session 4: Parallel Tracks Joint Strategies and Convergence</i>
09:45 - 10:15	<i>Synthesis</i>
10:15 - 10:45	<i>Break</i>
10:45 - 12:00	<i>Working Session 5: Charting Activities</i>
12:00 - 12:45	<i>Lunch and project interest groups (prep pitches)</i>
12:45 - 01:30	<i>Pilot project pitches</i>
01:30 - 2:00	<i>Reflections, Next Steps, Wrap up</i>